

EXPLORING THE PROFESSIONAL PREPARATION AND WORKING ENVIRONMENT OF TEACHERS IN UPSKILLING THEIR PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES

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ABSTRACT

The main concern of this study focused on the perception of teachers with regards to the professional preparation and working environment and its relationship to their professional competencies as they perform their duties. The study made use of the descriptive method of research utilizing correlational technique to determine the professional preparation and working environment of teachers in upskilling their professional competencies. There were 239 teachers from sixteen schools in Ibaan District, Division of Batangas who were involved in the study. The main data gathering instruments used was sets of questionnaire using google form. Responses were interpreted using the following statistical tools: frequency count and percent distribution, mean, standard deviation, pearson product – moment correlation coefficient and multiple linear regression. The respondents perceived the professional preparation of teachers with respect to knowledge as teaching skills, digital competencies, formative assessment and classroom management as well as the professional upgrading and attitude as “Very True to me (VT)”. The working environment of teachers with respect to class sizes, job autonomy, job complexity, morale, opportunities for advancement, policies and procedures, recognition and awards, satisfaction with school management, working relationship, work values and feedback as “Strongly Agree (SA) / “Very Engaging” (VE)”. The teachers’ professional competencies with respect to knowledge transmission, mentoring, student’s skills development, academic guidance and student attitude development as “Very True to me (VT)”. The professional preparation of teachers such as knowledge, professional upgrading and attitude significantly affect their professional competencies. The teachers’ working environment affect their professional competencies. Since it was found out that the professional preparation of teachers such as knowledge, professional upgrading, attitude and working environment significantly affect their professional competencies, the school administrators may encourage the teachers to pursue their graduate studies, seminars, trainings and the like may be of great help to upskill their professional competencies.

Keywords: Professional preparation, working environment, professional competencies